

Picturing concrete matters

AN ARCHAEOGRAPHY OF LEBANESE DESTROYED FAMILY HOMES

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Résumé: Une Archéographie de la destruction de maisons familiales libanaises

Malgré la tumultueuse reconstruction des dernières décennies, Beyrouth offre encore plusieurs possibilités d'étudier archéologiquement les restes de la guerre civile libanaise (1975-1990), tandis que les restes inhérents à cette même époque sont plus rares en périphérie et dans les campagnes. Les bâtiments détruits et pas encore investis par des chantiers de construction hypertrophiques, les demeures abandonnées ou les maisons familiales défigurées par les bombes et les balles sont omniprésents dans la vie matérielle du Liban actuel. Sur la base de deux cas d'étude, cet article présente quelques résultats d'une approche visuelle et archéologique très particulière des ruines de la guerre, à la fois à Beyrouth et à Qleiaat (au Mont Liban), où l'Ifpo et le Musée de Préhistoire Libanaise ont mis en place un programme conjoint. Bien que destiné à la réalisation d'une mission de prospections et fouilles des vestiges néolithiques, chalcolithiques et du début de l'âge du Bronze, ce projet a aussi pris en compte les ruines du passé récent en ayant recours à une approche « archéographique », à savoir une méthode interpolant archéologie et photographie, en utilisant la photographie comme un outil de documentation archéologique. L'« archéographie » ne consiste pas simplement en des images des ruines : elle implique plutôt une attitude d'anatomiste par rapport aux lieux et aux événements, à documenter par les images de leurs culture matérielle. Car, au-delà des mémoires conflictuelles, passées sous silence ou perdues, des questions telles « qu'est-ce qui s'est passé ici ? », « quand ? », et « comment cela s'est-il produit ? » sont intimement liées à une relation archéologique avec la réalité matérielle.

Mots-clefs: Guerre Civile Libanaise, Beyrouth, Qleiaat, archéographie, maisons familiales.

Abstract: Despite a tumultuous reconstruction in the last decades, Beirut still offers many opportunities to integrate landscape studies and archaeology of the Lebanese Civil War (1975-1990), while war ruins are rarer in the countryside. However, destroyed buildings still neglected by recent hypertrophic real estates, shattered houses or family homes disfigured by bombs and bullets are omnipresent in the Lebanese material life. Based on two case-studies, this paper presents some results of a specific visual and archaeological engagement with the war ruins both in Beirut and in Qleiaat (Mount Lebanon), where Ifpo and the Museum of Lebanese Prehistory have carried out a joined archaeological program. Intended as a mission of survey and excavations focused on Neolithic, Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age vestiges, this project is also taking into account the ruins of the recent past by an “archaeographic” approach, namely a method at the intersection between archaeology and photography, where the latter is a documental instrument for the first one. Archaeography is not simply about picturing ruins, but rather about a forensic attitude towards places and events, documented through the image of their material culture. Because, beyond conflicting, silenced or lost memories, questions like “what happened here?”, “when?”, and “how it happened?” intimately deal with an archaeological engagement with materiality.

Keywords: Lebanese civil war, Beirut, Qleiaat, archaeography, family homes.

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تصوير القضايا الملبوسة: دراسة أثرية مصورة للنازل اللبنانية المدمرة

على الرغم من إعادة الإعمار المضطربة في العقود الأخيرة، لا تزال بيروت توفر العديد من الاحتمالات لدراسة البقايا الأثرية لمخلفات الحرب الأهلية اللبنانية (1975-1990)، في حين أن البقايا الأصيلة في هذه الفترة نادرة في المحيط وفي الريف. المباني التي دُمرت لم تشغلها بعد مشاريع البناء الضخمة، والمنازل المهجورة أو المنازل العائلية المشوهة بواسطة القنابل والرصاص موجودة في كل مكان في الحياة المادية للبنان اليوم. يعرض هذا المقال استناداً إلى حالي دراسة بعض النتائج لنهج بصري وأثري خاص جداً بأطلال الحرب وذلك في كل من بيروت وقلبيات (في جبل لبنان)، حيث أُعد كل من الايفو ومتحف ما قبل التاريخ اللبناني برنامجاً مشتركاً لذلك. على الرغم من أنه تم الانتهاء من تنفيذ مهمة المسح والتنقيب لسويات العصر الحجري الحديث والعصر الحجري النحاسي والعصر البرونزي المبكر، إلا أن هذا المشروع أخذ في الاعتبار أنقاض الماضي القريب من خلال اللجوء إلى مقارنة "أثرية مصورة" من خلال استيفاء الآثار والتصوير الفوتوغرافي، وذلك باستخدام التصوير الفوتوغرافي كأداة توثيق أثرية. "علم الآثار الصوري" لا يتألف ببساطة من صور من الأنقاض، بل يأخذ موقف الطب الشرعي للأماكن والأحداث، من خلال توثيق صور ثقافتهم المادية. فبالرغم من الذكريات المتضاربة، التي تم إسكاتها أو ضياعها، أسئلة مثل "ماذا حدث هنا؟ متى؟ وكيف حدث هذا؟ ترتبط ارتباطاً وثيقاً بعلاقة أثرية مع الواقع المادي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الحرب الأهلية اللبنانية، بيروت، قلبيات، الآثار، المنازل العائلية.

ويته ركردني باره به رده سته كان: ليكولينه وهى شوينه وارى خانوى خانواده لوبنانيه كان

سهره راي دووباره بنياتمانه وهى بينايه تيكچوه وهى كان له سالاني رابردودا، شارى بهيروت زور ته گهر ده بيت بؤ ليكولينه وهى شوينه وارى پاشماوه شوينه واره كاني جهنگي ناوخوي لوباني (1975-1990)، لهو كانه دا پاشماوه كاني تهو سهرده مه زور به ده گهن مانوه له ده وروبه ر و لادبكاندا. تهو بينايانه ي ويرانكران له تيسنادا هيچ بينايه يه كي گه وره له جيگاي درووست نه كراون، وه خانوه جيپلراوه كان يا خانوه خانواده يه شيويندراويه كان له ريگاي بومب و جهك دا، له هه موو شوينيكدا له زياني مادي لوباني ته مرؤكه دا هه يه به پشت به ستن به دوو بارى ليكولينه وه كه ماندا، تهو تويرينه وه هه ندى ته نجاي بهرچاوى خسته روو له سهر شوينه وار و پاشماوه كاني جهنگ، له هه موو شوينيكى بهيروت و قه لايه كان (شاخه كاني لوبان)، لهو شوينه ي كه وا لييه Ifpo وه موزه خانهى پيش ميرووى لوباني پروگراميكي هاوبه شي دانا. هه رجه نده كوتاي هات به ليكولينه وه له پيشه ي پشكين له هه لكولين و چاخى به ردى نوى و جاني برونزي كوتاي، به لام تهو پروزه يه به ومه به سته ي ده كريت بؤ رزگار كردني پاشماوه ي رابردوى زيكي له ريگاي زيكي (شوينه وار)، بريته له ريگاي رزگار كردني شوينه وار و وينه گرتيان، ته موش له ريگاي وينه گرتن وهك نامراز يكي به به لگه كردني شوينه وارى. زانستى شوينه وار ته نها وينه ي پاشماوه كان له خو نا گريت: به لكو هه لويستى قه زاني به رامبه ر به شوين و رووداوه كان ده دوينت، بؤ به به لگه كردني له ريگاي وينگرتنى كلتوره ماديه كان. سه باره ت به وهى له پشت ياده وه ريه كاندا هه ن، كه وا له ريگايه وه ده كريت بيده نك بگريت يا له ده ست بدرت، پرسيارى وهك ته مه ((ته مه چي روويدا؟)) وه كه ي؟ وه چون ته مه روويدا؟ به شيويه يكي باش به به يوه نديه شوينه واره يه كان به ستراوه له گهل واقعي مادي دا.

ووشه ي تيه ر: چهنگي ناوخه ي لوبنا، بهيروت، قلبيات، شوينه وار، خانوى خيزاني.

تصوير بردارى اجسام بتني/كانكريتي: باستان شناسي خانه هاي فاميلي ويران شده لبنان

باوجود بازسازی های سریع دهه های اخیر، هنوز هم این امکان در بيروت وجود دارد، که بقایای جنگ داخلی لبنان (1975-1990) را از نظر باستانشناسی مطالعه نمایم، گرچند بقایای اشاره شده حتی در آن زمان در روستاها و در حومه شهرها اندک بودند. در لبنان امروز، مسکن های متروک، ساختمان های ویران شده، که تاحال مورد بازسازی و ترمیم قرار نگرفته اند و خانه های فامیلی که توسط گلوله ها و بمب ها تخریب شده اند، قابل مشاهده اند.

براساس دو مطالعه موردی، این مقاله به تشریح نتایج بصری و باستانشناختی از بقایای جنگ در بيروت و قلبيات (جبل-لبنان) می پردازد، جای که مؤسسه فرانسوی خاور نزدیک و موزه/موزیم ما قبل تاریخ لبنان برنامه مشترکی را بنیان گذاشته اند. در کنار تکمیل مأموریت سروی ها و کاوش ها بقایای دوره نوسنگی، عصر مس سنگی و آغاز دوران برنز، این مأموریت بقایای دوره های پسین را نیز با استفاده از یک روش «باستان نگاری 1»، که روش مشترک باستانشناسی و عکسبرداری است؛ مطالعه می کند. در این روش عکسبرداری، منحنی یک وسیله اسناد سازی آثار باستانی تلقی میگردد. «باستان نگاری 2» تنها تصاویر مخروبه ها را در برنمی گیرد، این روش بیشتر گرایش قضائی در مورد مکان ها و وقایع دارد، که این فرهنگ مادی را بواسطه تصاویر اسناد سازی نماید. بخاطریکه فراتر از خاطرات جنگی، سکوت و فراموشی، پرسش هایی چون: «چی واقعه ای اینجا گذشته؟»، «چی وقت؟» و اینکه «چگونه بوجود آمده؟» روابط عمیقی با باستان شناسی و واقعیت مادی دارند.

واژه های کلیدی: جنگ داخلی لبنان، بيروت، قلبيات، باستان نگاری، خانه های فامیلی.

AN HISTORICAL INTRODUCTION

A CRITICAL appreciation of historical archaeology as a practice dealing with recent conflicts requires a firm grounding in memory theory, specifically the formation and contestation of memory narratives. But, first of all, it requires specific material-cultural approaches intended to reconstruct historical dynamics. This paper focuses on an archaeological record of some ruins of the Lebanese civil war: a visual-material archaeology of circumstantial, intimate and unknown aspects of a well-known conflict. Because of its geopolitical complexity, this war has become the example of civil war *par excellence*, as well as a topic of theoretical-political reflection about the disintegration of a state.

The origins of the Lebanese civil war are rooted in the political-religious communitarianism (reinforced since the mandate of the French colonial power – 1920-1943), as well as in the disintegration within the framework of the Cold War, after the establishment of the state of Israel and the displacement to Lebanon of a hundred thousand Palestinian refugees. These ones changed the demographic balance of the country in favour of the Muslim population². The militarization of some Palestinian groups, with the arrival of the PLO forces after their expulsion from Jordan during Black September, sparked an arms race amongst the different Lebanese political factions. Fighting between Maronite and Palestinian forces began in 1975, and Left Wing, pan-Arabist and Muslim Lebanese groups later al-

lied themselves with the Palestinians. During the course of the fighting, alliances shifted rapidly and unpredictably: by the end of the war, nearly every party had allied with and subsequently betrayed every other party at least once³. Furthermore, foreign powers meddled in the war and fought alongside different factions. Since 1976, Syrian troops entered Lebanon, and went on their presence until 2005. The Israeli (1978-2000) involvement, initially targeted against the Palestinian organizations, implied a military invasion from the South, a siege of Beirut (1982-1983) and included amongst its consequences the massacre of Palestinians in the refugee camps of Sabra and Chatila, carried on by Maronite groups. Peace keeping forces, such as the Multinational Force in Lebanon and UNIFIL, were also stationed in Lebanon. The Taif Agreement of 1989 marked the beginning of the end of the fighting. In March 1991, parliament passed an amnesty law that pardoned all political crimes prior to its enactment.

Mainly due to the persistent sectarian tensions⁴, in many respects, peace and political dynamics have been built as a continuation of war by other means. Destroyed Lebanese family homes retain not only traces of the violence that, during the war, has demolished them, but also the trauma that, after the war, has silenced individual and collective memories. In this sense, they represent an interesting case-study for an archaeological study of the material culture of the civil war.

A VISUAL-ARCHAEOLOGICAL APPROACH

Despite the growth in the last ten years of the so-called archaeology of the contemporary past as academic field⁵, archaeological sensibility, methods and studies are rarely associated with recent ruins or remains. In social disciplines, much attention has been devoted to how memory crystallizes into sites or places of memory, locations of collective remembering⁶ considered as decisive for some kind of past events. So, memory is generally associated with a “re-collective” notion, as a conscious and

wilful human process of recalling the past. Conversely, archaeological practice is mostly concerned with a different kind of sites, too conflicting, intimate, prosaic or repulsive to be shaped as collective memory⁷. These places are also *materially* related to another kind of memory: a habit memory⁸. While re-collective memory implies a conscious gaze directed towards a particular past, habit memory is an implicit act of re-membering embedded in our bodily routines and ways of dealing with things:

2. CORM 2003.

3. FISK 2001.

4. CORM 2003.

5. See for instance SHANKS 2004; SCHOFIELD 2005; GONZÁLEZ-RUIBAL 2008.

6. NORA 1984; ASSMANN 1992.

7. DOMANSKA 2005.

8. CONNERTON 1989.

“it no longer represents our past to us, it acts it”⁹. In Bergson’s formative conception, habit memory was largely a function of adaptive value: only those aspects of the past that are useful or compatible with our present conducts are habitually remembered. Remains dealing with what was once useful, and thus embedded in repetitious practice and infused with habit memory. When discarded, outmoded or shattered, their habitual mnemonic significance is lost while their physical presence, albeit ruined, continues.

In other words, beyond people once involved with ruins and who retains any direct memory about them, archaeological sites have an intrinsic capability to triggering habit memory as an involuntary remembrance¹⁰, becoming potential agents of disruption and “actualisation”. Precisely by being redundant and discarded, they reveal the gaps in the idealized construction of history as progress and continuous narrative; they bring forth the abject memories that both the recollective and the habitual have displaced. Moreover, these ordinary sites and their associated events (collectively forgotten because sometimes too trivial, sometimes too traumatic) open up some glimmers to observe a silenced past. In other words, investigating these sites is an effective means of historical knowledge.

In this sense, the archaeology of the domestic ruins produced by the Lebanese civil war is a very “normal” archaeological topic. Ruins of a family home are not a formal place of memory: they have nothing official, collective or monumental; they are the site of a tragedy without any emphasis, a calamity and a defeat that are always private, even when repeated on a very large scale. Besides, the dream of every archaeologist (mainly prehistoric archaeologists like me) is to find a burned house, destroyed or abandoned after a sudden and traumatic event, which has preserved the context of the everyday life: a kind of little Pompeii with all the furnishings in their place¹¹. I think there is something wicked and anti-scientific in the fact that the chronological distance from the documented context is directly proportional to the emotional detachment¹². However, a (pre-historic or contemporary) ruined house is a context, namely a tangible frame of what remains of past events and relationships.

Therefore, nature, size, quantity, relative position, depositional arrangements of the objects, as well as masonries and their degree of integrity have been photographically recorded.

In itself, this practice matches with the everyday behaviour of any kind of archaeologist on any kind of field-yard. But this kind of photographic archive does not aim at being objective or exhaustive: it is rather intended to be a visual engagement with the specific kind of material-cultural *mise-en-scène* produced by past events¹³. *Mise-en-scène* is about staging: the disposition, arrangement and relationships between people, artefacts, places and happenings. In this sense, photography enables alternative and genuine statements about the past and provides a means to make manifest the heterogeneous and ineffable that often is left out of scientific prose¹⁴. “Archaeography” is a scientific tool lying at the intersection between archaeology and photography: the first is not just about the past and the second one is not just about images. The both create relationships and material-cultural connections between places and events, establishing a forensic attitude towards places and documenting what becomes during and after a given event. Archaeology works with what remains of the past; photography arrests its presence and consequences. Therefore “archaeography” records ruins not as an object of enchantment or as a romantic aesthetic fascination for dust, decay and loss. Ruins are not the chic entropic side of war, they are not photographed for some kind of pornographic attraction towards destruction and pain: they are just recorded as an archaeological material when excavations or further investigations are materially impossible.

From a purely methodological point of view, archaeology consists in taking things away from where they were found and turning them into an archive, a collection, that one can study, write about, and share. Photography consists in using a camera and a point of view to turn a relationship with something into a form one can take away, look at later and share with other people. Therefore, “archaeography” consists in giving visual, (photo)graphic form to such relationships with the remains of the past, in order to share and study these material-cultural relationships.

9. BERGSON 1896, p. 93.

10. BENJAMIN 1936.

11. BOISSINOT 1990.

12. GINZBURG 1998.

13. SHANKS & SVABO 2013, p. 89-90.

14. See the “Opening Dialogs in Archaeological Photography” and the exposition organized during the Theoretical Archaeological Group (TAG) USA 2011 (University of Berkley 5/6th-8th/2011) <https://www.flickr.com/photos/28768805@N00/galleries/72157626457055744/?rb=1>, <https://www.flickr.com/photos/28768805@N00/galleries/72157626462396599/?rb=1>

Figure 1: a: Map of Beirut with the location of Damascus Street.
b: Beirut. Current appearance of Damascus Street, close to the Ifpo and to Sodeco Square.

TWO CASE-STUDIES: FAMILY HOMES DESTROYED BY THE LEBANESE CIVIL WAR

The first case-study has to do with a densely inhabited zone of the Lebanese capital. It is about the destroyed family homes situated along a short segment of the demarcation line between East and West Beirut. It coincides with *Tariq ash-Shâm Sharia* (Damascus Street), south of Sodeco Square and north of

Furn ach-Chabbak¹⁵ (Figure 1 a). Both these areas have known lasting and bloody clashes during the '80s, with snipers stably occupying a famous sighted building in Sodeco, and car bombs and frequent street battles around the almost fortified Christian enclave of Furn ach-Chabbak. The Ifpo (French Institute for the

Figure 2: a, b, c: Beirut. Impacts of bullets on plastered façades.
d: Beirut. Broken staircases and windows sealed with concrete blocks to protect the snipers.

Figure 3: Beirut. Family homes destroyed by fire on the ancient Green Line of Damascus Street.

Near East) is situated in this sector of Damascus Street, where residential buildings and family homes have been massively destroyed. Indeed, a fundamental distinction between East and West Beirut is present in the mental map of every inhabitant of the Lebanese capital, so that the expression “going from west to east” is still both a way to mean a physical shift, and a way to express a potential danger.

Nevertheless, the current urban landscape is completely banalized within the metropolitan panorama of the tumultuous reconstruction of the last decades: the eastern and western sides of the road appear quite similar and real estate prices are the same throughout the area (Figure 1 b). Very few destroyed buildings remain. From the point of view of their architectural typology, they have a peculiar aspect. This is due both to the injuries they suffered and to their structure, with two or three storeys

and plastered façades. Recent buildings are concrete and steel multi-storey palaces or towers. On the other hand, plaster was widespread since the '20s and radically affects the general appearance of the ruins: impacts of bullets or mortars on the walls represent their most characteristic and visible trait. Wherever, the layer of plaster on the external surfaces show irregular burst of perforations with unequal holes bordered by splashes (Figure 2 a, b, c). Even for the buildings still standing, most of time the depth and strength of the impacts has knocked down all appendices: terraces are wrecked, external stairs have collapsed, and columns of the arcades are broken (Figure 2 d). Openings have been reduced to slits: windows have been sealed with concrete blocks in order to protect the snipers who squatted the buildings from other snipers, in other buildings.

The archaeological reading of the domestic plans, as well as

of the everyday life in these houses is almost impossible even for the ancient owners. They decipher the images slowly, according to an archaeological process of interpretation: “This is the corner of the bedroom?...The bathroom floor was there?”¹⁶.

Strangely, in the area of Beirut that was (and remains) known for the war of the snipers, houses tell a partially different and untold story¹⁷. Bullets did not force families to leave. Family homes, turned in little fortresses to protect inhabitants first and snipers then, were besieged and look as little citadels. Their external pipes of water and gas are cut, exterior walls did not constitute a sufficient barrier: destruction came through the windows, grenades shuttered interior walls and definitive devastation took place like in prehistoric times, by means of fire (Figure 3 a, b). For the owners and their descendants, these are sites of silenced memories and secluded pain: suffering is always private and exclusive; faults are always attributed to the “others”

The most frequent reaction front of the photographic archaeological documentation is a kind of acknowledgement. The recollection follows an analogical procedure, starting from the material evidences and using memories to verify the reading of the ruins. An archaeographic record requires to deal with the chaotic mess of rubble, debris, fragments and scattered objects: an ordered and neat image of the past material life is re-composed backwards, on the basis of the disorder of the ruins and starting from the entropy caused by violence. Owners of the ruined homes are not the only ones concerned by this involuntary memorial process. Even in front of pictures of unknown houses, recorded in other districts or in other cities, often the genuine and spontaneous reaction is a sort of identification: “Yes, I know this zone. . . .” Many people recognize (often wrongly) as belonging to their political-religious community the ruined homes and are ready to accuse other communities of their destruction: pain is always a private concern, while faults always belong to the outside world¹⁸.

Now, rejected by the collective consciousness, unusable by the public discourse in support of national unity, unnecessary for the creeping communitarianist propaganda, the destroyed family homes are simply destined to disappear.

The second case-study is about the destroyed family homes at Qleiaat, in the Mount Lebanon (Figure 4 a, b). Between 2015 and 2017, Ifpo and the Museum of Lebanese Prehistory carried out a mission of surveys and excavations at Qleiaat as a joined archaeological program. The Qleiaat project is mainly focused on late Neolithic, Chalcolithic and Early Bronze vestiges, namely on the emergence of the first urbanization in an area (wrongly) considered so far as a Levantine cultural periphery. But the field research has also taken into account the ruins of the recent past of Qleiaat. Here, towards the end of the civil war there have been many severe clashes between Christian militias¹⁹. The fights that in those years have opposed (especially in Beirut) Maronite and Orthodox armed groups are a somewhat known episode of the final phase of the war. But so far there was no evidence attesting of so hard clashes outside the capital.

The material culture manifests some banal aspects of the everyday life in a Christian village of the Mount Lebanon during the '80s. An enormous number of spoons and forks, bottles (of alcohol), plates and tableware show the importance traditionally attributed to hospitality, while several boxes of an Egyptian laxative suggest some consequences of this social love for food (Figure 5 a, b, c). Some furniture is still in place: shelves, armchairs, drawers containing lingerie and medicines, books and bags (Figure 6 a, b). Movable items inherent to the fighting have their industrial and trade codes indicating their origin (mainly Russia, Italy, France and Yugoslavia), as well as their date of production: they were all quite recent, assembled between the end of the '70s and the middle of the '80s (Figure 6 c). Other objects show the first consequences of the clashes: suitcases everywhere, both empty and full, abandoned in a hurry, open wardrobes, beds that still have their sheets, newspaper

16. KANAFANI-ZAHAR 2011, p. 165-169.

17. At the northern end of Damascus Street in Sodeco Square is situated the so-called Barakat Building, also known as the Yellow House. In 1924, this beautiful and surprising structure was originally designed for the Barakat family, featuring an avant-garde architectural transparency, and connecting the residents to the city through its unique central void and through its whimsical facade that sweeps on a 270° angle. With the outbreak of the civil war in 1975, fire and violence left the structure destroyed, abandoned and disconnected from the urban area. Eventually it became a war machine, as militias moved in and abused its architectural genius. In particular, because of the wide angle of the façade, the Barakat Building became the most famous nest of snipers in the city. From there, protected by the massive structure of the edifice, they were able to patiently disseminate death on two main streets: Avenue Elias Sarkis to the west and the Green Line (Damascus Street) to the south. The Barakat Building has been currently turned into Beit Beirut (the Museum of Memory of the City of Beirut) and it is open to the public since September 2017 (<http://www.beitbeirut.org/english/>).

18. ROLLAND 2003.

19. PICARD 2002.

Figure 4: a: Location of Qleiaat, in the central region of the Mount Lebanon (Google Maps).
b: A view of Beirut and its bay from Qleiaat (about 1080 m above sea level).

Figure 5: Qleiaat. Material culture inherent to the love for food and to its consequences: tableware, alcoholic spirits and laxatives.

dating back to 1988, overturned books, female cosmetics left in bathroom cabinets (Figure 7 a, b, c).

Then, walls and staircases, destroyed and partially reconstructed masonries indicate how clashes have become a lasting battle. Once abandoned, family homes have been occupied by militias who have exploited some damages of the walls as firing stations to threat the lower part of the village (Figure 8 a, b, c). Qleiaat is a mountain village: winters are long and very cold. Many books and furnishings have been burnt to warm the fighters occupying these devastated architectures full of holes. War is a boring occupation, so they made a lot of graffiti on the walls: obscene pictures, caricatures, prayers, signatures, mutual offenses, insults against the enemy and attempts of self-portrait are intertwined, drawn with pens, pencils, cigarette remains or spark plugs – an iconographic repertoire crossing both the imagination and the ordinary life of the fighters (Figures 9 and 10).

At Qleiaat, everyone remembers these events: many dis-

placed families have returned to live in the village (but not in the same houses); Abuna Youssef Mubarak, the priest of the Maronite parish, was a child when he was injured in a leg; some owners of the destroyed family homes are still alive. The inter-Christian clashes during the last years of the civil war are a haunting presence²⁰, but no one speaks about the fact that a war never ends peacefully. The destroyed family homes are ancient wounds, places that have never been considered attractive by official commemorations and that are now more and more concealed, buried and removed from the public space for the benefit of a shining renewal. Qleiaat is become a more and more nice-looking mountain resort, with a lot of recent apartments and hotels.

Given the generalized absence interest in war ruins, it is clear that a problem arises for archaeography as a means of investigation and documentation of this kind of material realities. In other words, what is the meaning and purpose of an archaeological approach to the war ruins ?

20. HANF 1993.

a

b

c

Figure 6: a, b: Qleiaat. Furniture still *in situ*.
c: Qleiaat. Russian weapon.

a

b

c

Figure 7: Qleiaat. Material culture of a hasty abandonment.

a

b

c

d

e

Figure 8: Qleiaat. Abandoned family homes turned into firing positions.

Figure 9: Qleiaat. Graffiti made by occupant militias in the abandoned family homes.

a

b

c

Figure 10: Qleiaat. Graffiti made by occupant militias in the abandoned family homes.

CONCLUSIONS: PICTURING PERSISTING AND OFTEN UNKNOWN PASTS

In *The Eighteenth Brumaire of Louis Bonaparte*, Karl Marx²¹ wrote that people make their own history, not as they please, “but under circumstances directly encountered, given and transmitted from the past. The tradition of all dead generations weighs like a nightmare on the brains of the living” . Sometimes this burden becomes particularly massive and viscous because past is never past. Archaeology deals with these problems, but it is not the solution and does not produce solutions. On the one side, its aim is to re-construct histories and to produce material cultural tales. On the other side, it cannot ignore memory (and its political implications) as fundamental and basic component of the archaeological narrative. This de-ontological and methodological dilemma is the same both for the prehistory and for the recent past. In Lebanon (and elsewhere), the better solution to heal the wounds of a shattered social conscience probably does not lie amongst the ruins of family homes or other forgotten sites marked by war and violence. Nevertheless, archaeological approaches (as archaeological photography) to sites marginalized and not touched by the official or monumental commemorations have demonstrated, as a secondary effect of the archaeological-historical investigation, their capability to produce intimate and individual re-compositions of broken and traumatised memories. These approaches allow us to study the past (in order to know it) and to experience it (in order to acknowledge it).

Materially, the past does not exist as a sequence of events, and never did. Archaeologists never encounter time as date, flow or sequence. Ontologically the past is all around us, mingling, merging, decaying, disappearing in the present. The past exists just as material relations, intermingling remains that persist through time by qualities of durability, which varies according to things and contexts²². This generates *kairos* or actuality: the presence²³ of the (remains of) the past in the present, and therefore the possibility of working on the past-in-the-present, just as memory. Memory is not in itself a coherent account of the past, but a process of discrete iterative acts of recollection, involuntary habit memory, present moments prompting con-

nections with something that remains. In this, archaeology is work performed upon remains of the past. Photography is a mode of engagement between past and present characterized by an articulating temporality of *kairos*, a conjunctive moment of past/present²⁴. It associates past events and relations with present places: “this happened here”²⁵. In the same time, dynamics are integral to an archaeographic record: the photograph is mobile, he changes the angle, explores different perspectives addressing questions such as “How might the past be adequately represented? How might imagery document an event authentically?” . Especially if these relations and events deal with the everyday, the quotidian, photography can deliver an enormous archive of contemporary everyday mundane life in any single shot.

In this sense, sometimes archaeography proves its own capability to provide intimate memorial closure. The question that remains is: what is the social and political price for personal closure? According to Bruno Latour²⁶, there are many types of gatherings which are not political in the customary sense, but which bring a public together around particular things: laboratories, marketplaces, museums. Archaeography of the ruined family homes creates a particular ‘parliament of things’ that brings together objects, people and discourses. These are, however, parliaments that many want closed, dismembered or dissolved. In Lebanon, after the civil war, sharing the pain also means sharing the blame. Therefore, the removal of sins and ruins is a perfect and convenient solution for the communitarist framework of the society, but awkward and dire for the individuals and their families: a way to accommodate a sectarian peace and to feed private grudges.

However, beyond the acknowledgment of the past, archaeography also investigates it. And, in this sense, sometimes, its result is an archaeological discovery. This expression could seem meaningless if associated to the understanding of some circumstances of a very recent and ordinary past as the family homes destroyed by the Lebanese civil war. Nevertheless, it sounds good to speak of discovery if it is about a war of some

21. MARX 1852, p. 5.

22. HODDER 2012.

23. RUNIA 2006.

24. BARTHES 1980, p. 22-31, 50-51.

25. SONTAG 1977.

26. LATOUR 2005.

thousand years ago. One could object that, for the recent past, we already have images, texts and other historical sources, therefore it is useless to investigate some fresh scars by archaeological means. It is the same objection many scholars were used to make some decades ago about medieval archaeology. Moreover, one could also consider that individual memories are sufficient to convey and spread knowledge about domestic aspects of the recent past. It is the same objection anthropologists have had to deal with when they began to question the accuracy and reliability of the answers they receive during their interviews. Indeed, it is an archaeological truism that in the recent as in the ancient past, public or domestic aspects of traumatic, trivial, or shaming events have never been publicly documented. In the same way, it is obvious that individual memories about a silenced past do not convey nor spread any knowledge: memories can be, distorted, confused or perfectly silent. It is the case of the public records and individual memories about family homes destroyed during the Lebanese civil war.

On the one hand, even if life and death along the “Green Line” of Damascus Street in Beirut is a well-documented topic (made familiar by photos, cinema, personal stories, newspaper articles, etc.), there is no longer any document nor archive about timing and circumstances of the displacement of the families who lived in the area. On the other hand, even if many inhabitants still live at Qleiaat and have very fresh memories of the

clashes, the battle for this mountain village between Christian militias is a major episode of the end of the civil war which has never been recorded by any media nor official file. These are little (but significant) archaeological discoveries, that confirm an obvious reality: archaeology of recent conflicts is a conflicting subject, which can offer information that cannot be found in any other way.

Archaeography appears, therefore, as a means of knowledge and acknowledgement because it is a process of “manifestation”²⁷. This manifestation can be at least as important as the construction of narratives, in the usual sense of the term, and it has the added advantage of being less dangerous for the saturation of memory. Manifesting implies re-membering things and being less an historian, who writes stories, and more an archaeologist, who works with material remains that are not always reducible to mere text. Images of the ruined family homes deeply contrast with the fierce memorial rhetoric of every political-religious Lebanese community. In themselves, they do not produce a new memorial narrative: they are just an archaeological disclosure of the banality of the war, where everyday life is lost. This simple archaeography of bullets and masonries deals with the “unsayable” and the “un-constituted” that lie outside the official discourse²⁸. Because, as Sontag said, “narratives can make us understand. Photographs do something else: they haunt us”²⁹.

27. SHANKS 2004.

28. GONZÁLEZ-RUIBAL 2008, p. 255.

29. SONTAG 2003, p. 89.

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